

PREPARATION OF 4-THIAZOLIDONES AND THEIR 5-(p)-SULPHONAMIDOPHENYL-AZO DERIVATIVES

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Fifteen different 2-arylimino-4-thiazolidones have been synthesised by two different methods, and the yields obtained by both the methods have been compared. The resulting thiazolidone compounds have been coupled with diazotised sulphanilamide giving rise to fifteen different 5-sulphonamidophenyl-azo derivatives. Experimental evidence has been adduced to support the observation that the azo group is linked to the CH₂ group in 5-position of the thiazolidone nucleus.

In view of the close relationship between thiazole and thiazolidones and the reported use of thiazolidone compounds as anaesthetics (Surrey, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 3354), anticonvulsants (Troutman and Long, *ibid.*, 1948, 70, 3436) and amoebacidal agents (Surrey and Cutler, *ibid.*, 1954, 76, 578), it was considered worthwhile to carry out investigations for preparing new types of 4-thiazolidone derivatives and explore new directions of applications of the resulting compounds.

Thiazolidone compounds have been synthesised by various methods (Surrey, *ibid.*, 1947, 69, 2911; Ratnar and Clarke, *ibid.*, 1937, 59, 200; Mathes and Stewart, *ibid.*, 1950, 72, 1879). In the present investigation fifteen different 2-arylimino-4-thiazolidones have been prepared by two methods, and the yields obtained in both the methods have been compared. In the first method, already reported (Das and Rout, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 617), aryl-substituted thioureas were condensed with monochloroacetic acid in alcohol in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate. The reaction proceeds according to the following scheme, leading to a product of the following structure.

Reasons for assigning the thiazolidone structure to the above compounds have already been reported (Das and Rout, *loc. cit.*).

The second method adopted involves condensation of ethyl monochloroacetate with arylthioureas in absolute alcohol using sodium ethoxide as the condensing agent. The yields obtained in each case by both the methods have been compared and are recorded in Table I.

Both the experimental procedures are illustrated in the experimental in the preparation of 2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone.

The thiazolidone compounds prepared above have been coupled with diazotised sulphanilamide. It has been assumed that the azo group is attached to the thiazolidone nucleus in position-5; the assumption is based on the following evidences. Bogert and Cherboff (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 2864; *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1924, **10**, 418) obtained dyes by coupling diazotised *p*-nitroaniline and sulphanilic acid with 2-aminothiazole in which they observed that the azo group was attached to position-5 of the thiazole nucleus. Ganapathi and Venkataraman (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, **22A**, 348) and Beyer and Wolter (*Chem. Ber.*, 1952, **85**, 1077) confirmed the above observations; the former workers used this reaction for the preparation of 5-amino-2-hydroxythiazoles. On account of a close resemblance between thiazole and thiazolidones, the same behaviour is also expected of thiazolidones.

Meerwein, Buchner and Rögster (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1939, **152**, 237) after a detailed study of the reactions of diazonium salts with $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated carbonyl compounds concluded that the arylazo group entered the position α to the activating group. This is also supported by the work of Kvalnes (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 2478) and Freund (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1943), who made use of this reaction in preparing 2-aryl-1:4-benzoquinones and 3-*p*-arsonophenylcoumarin. In thiazolidones, the CH₂ group in position-5 is in α -position to the activating carbonyl group; hence, the placement of the azo group in position-5 is justified. Zeigler has also made similar observations in case of pyrazolones and formulated the structure of the yellow dye, Tartrazine, accordingly.

This conclusion gains further support from the fact that when the CH₂ group in position-5 of the thiazolidone nucleus is blocked by condensation with atomic aldehyde or by substitution of the hydrogen atoms by alkyl groups, which could be easily achieved by replacing chloroacetic acid or ester by α -bromoisobutyric acid or ester in the synthesis of thiazolidone compound, no azo dye is formed.

The azo dye formed by coupling of diazotised sulphanilamide with 2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone has also been found to be inert towards condensation with aromatic aldehydes. This conclusively proves that the coupling takes place in position-5, i.e. at the CH₂ group, as shown below:

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Arylthioureas.—The phenyl- and *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolylthioureas were prepared by the action of alcoholic NH₃ on the corresponding isothiocyanates obtained by the methods of Dains and others (*"Organic Synthesis"*, Vol. I, p. 437). The *o*-, *m*- and *p*-(chloro-, carboxy- and nitro)-phenyl- and α - and β -naphthyl- thioureas were obtained by the action of ammonium thiocyanate on the hydrochlorides of the compounding bases (De Clermont, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, **31**, 71).

Preparation of 2-Phenylimino-4-thiazolidone: Method I.—Phenylthiourea (5 g.) was heated under reflux with monochloroacetic acid (4 g.) in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate (3 g.) and absolute alcohol (25 c.c.) on a water-bath for 3 to 4 hours. The reaction mixture was poured into water when a precipitate was formed. The precipitate was washed several times with boiling water and finally recrystallised from alcohol, yield 6 g., m.p. 175°. (Found: C, 56.65; H, 4.81; N, 13.39; S, 16.99. $C_9H_9ON_2S$ requires C, 56.25; H, 4.16; N, 14.58; S, 16.66 per cent).

Method II.—Phenylthiourea (6 g.) was heated under reflux with ethyl chloroacetate (4.8 g.) in presence of sodium ethoxide (5 g.) and 25 c.c. of absolute alcohol on a water-bath for 2 to 3 hours. The reaction mixture was poured into water and acidified with acetic acid when a precipitate was formed. The precipitate was washed several times with boiling water and finally recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 175°, yield 7.3 g. (Found: C, 55.78; H, 4.29; N, 14.31; S, 16.13. $C_9H_9ON_2S$ requires C, 56.25; H, 4.16; N, 14.58; S, 16.66 per cent).

Preparation of 5-(p)-sulphonamidophenylazo-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone.—Sulphanilamide (1 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (2 c.c.) and water (100 c.c.), was diazotised with $NaNO_2$ (0.5 g. in 30 c.c. of water) in an ice-bath. The resulting diazo solution was added gradually with stirring to a previously well cooled solution of 2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone (1 g.) in dilute NaOH solution (1 g. in 40 c.c. of water), kept in an ice-bath. After addition the reaction mixture was stirred for another hour. The orange-coloured dye separated out and was collected and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 85°, yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 48.0; H, 3.47; N, 18.66; S, 17.06. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3N_2S_2$ requires C, 47.25; H, 3.53; N, 17.95; S, 16.92 per cent).

TABLE I

2-Arylimino-4-thiazolidone (I).

Compound No.	Nature of aryl group R.	M. F.*	Yield by method		% Nitrogen.		% Sulphur.	
			I.	II	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1	Phenyl	175°	90%	95%	14.41	14.58	16.13	16.66
2	o-Tolyl	136°	85	87	13.87	13.59	14.97	15.53
3	m. „	160°	80	82	13.14	13.59	15.19	15.53
4	p. „	191°	75	82	12.79	13.59	15.65	15.53
5	o-Nitrophenyl	147°	50	60	...	...	13.32	13.50
6	m. „	210°	52	55	...	...	12.91	13.50
7	p. „	235°	55	60	...	...	12.83	13.50
8	o-Chlorophenyl	141°	65	70	11.58	12.31	14.01	14.13
9	m. „	181°	68	70	11.79	12.31	14.73	14.13
10	p. „	200°	70	75	11.98	12.31	13.97	14.13
11	o-Carboxyphenyl	190°	50	55	11.05	11.86	13.13	13.56
12	m. „	255°	53	55	12.06	11.86	13.86	13.56
13	p. „	>360°	51	56	10.58	11.86	12.77	13.56
14	α -Naphthyl	184°	90	95	11.07	11.57	13.52	13.22
15	β . „	220°	92	95	10.91	11.57	12.83	13.22

TABLE II

2-Arylimino-5-sulphonamidophenylazo-4-thiazolidones (II).

Compound No. **	Colour.	* M.P.	Yield.	% Nitrogen.		% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1	Orange	85°	50%	17.95	18.66	16.92	17.06
2	Deep yellow	102°	55	16.98	17.99	15.97	16.45
3	Brown	> 350°	58	17.53	17.99	15.72	16.45
4	Brown	285°	60	17.29	17.99	15.83	16.45
5	Dirty brown	70°	65	...	...	15.72	15.24
6	Yellow	112°	61	...	...	15.12	15.24
7	Brown	78°	56	...	...	14.89	15.24
8	Yellowish brown	118°	65	16.81	17.09	15.19	15.63
9	Yellow	195°	70	16.37	17.09	14.77	15.63
10	Orange	150°	71	17.51	17.09	15.83	15.63
11	Yellow	> 350°	50	16.21	16.70	14.98	15.27
12	Yellowish brown	> 350°	52	15.92	16.70	15.63	15.27
13	Yellowish brown	> 350°	56	16.81	16.70	15.19	15.27
14	Chocolate-red	105°	70	16.19	16.47	14.39	15.06
15	Orange-red	136°	78	16.05	16.47	14.81	15.06

* All the melting points have been taken on Gallencamp's electrically heated melting point apparatus.

** The nature of aryl group R corresponding to those in Table I.

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